

Geographic context and heart decompensation risks: Spatial association of socio-environmental determinants of health and heart valve disease in Northeast London

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Summary

Heart Valve Disease (HVD) requires timely diagnosis, yet delayed detection remains common. This study identifies high-risk neighborhoods, examines associations between HVD incidence and social and environmental determinants of health (SEDOH), and explores factors driving spatial patterns of HVD in selected Boroughs of Northeast London. Using a multi-step modeling framework, individual- and area-level relationships are analyzed alongside spatial clustering. Results reveal distinct high-risk clusters and show that ethnicity, air quality, employment, and health deprivation are key markers of HVD risk. These findings support targeted public health interventions and more equitable resource allocation for early HVD detection.

KEYWORDS: heart valve disease, natural language processing, spatial analysis

1. Introduction

Heart Valve Disease (HVD) is a form of cardiovascular disease (CVD) that requires early diagnosis to prevent severe health outcomes. When patients seek care at a late stage, referred to as acute or decompensated HVD, the risk to their lives increases significantly. Delayed diagnosis also places substantial operational pressure on hospitals, including bed shortages and increased staff workload, which can lead to deficiencies in service delivery. Diagnosis depends on the performance of a

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transthoracic echocardiogram, a common and reliable medical diagnostic test.

Despite the clear importance of early detection of HVD, many individuals are identified late. Beyond medical factors, this delay is often influenced by more complex mechanisms such as cultural hesitancy, socioeconomic challenges, limited healthcare access, and characteristics of the neighborhood environment. These social and environmental determinants of health (SEDOH) play a crucial role in shaping both HVD risk and diagnosis. In this context, identifying vulnerable areas of HVD and understanding their associated SEDOH can contribute to the development of a more efficient and equitable healthcare system that supports early detection for high-risk populations.

This research aims to: (1) identify high HVD risk neighborhoods, (2) examine the relationship between HVD incidence and SEDOH, and (3) determine the key factors that drive the spatial patterns of HVD incidence in Northeast London. We utilise a comprehensive SEDOH dataset across open-source data and attributes extracted from clinical records using natural language processing (NLP). Multi-step analytical modeling approaches are employed to uncover underlying relationships. Specifically, a logistic regression model is applied to reveal individual-level socio-demographic determinants, followed by a multivariate eigenvector spatial filtering (ESF) regression model to identify the geographical characteristics of the neighborhood associated with HVD risk at the Lower-layer Super Output Area (LSOA) level. For bridging individual-level profiles and spatial-level profiles, the iterative proportional fitting (IPF) procedure and post-stratification are utilized.

This research contributes to a better understanding of how various SEDOH relate to HVD risk, enabling the identification of underserved communities, supporting data-driven recommendations for clinic location planning, and promoting culturally responsive and equitable healthcare delivery for cardiovascular disease care.

2. Literature Review

Numerous studies have sought to identify epidemiological characteristics of broader CVDs, including HVD and the critical factors influencing their occurrence. Coffey et al. (2015, 2021) examined the contemporary epidemiology of various types of HVD, suggesting that the burden of HVD is closely associated with specific socio-demographic conditions (Yeung et al. 2013; d'Arcy et al. 2016; Biswas et al. 2025).

A systematic review by Mena et al. (2018) demonstrated that the spatial distribution of the various types of CVD is highly heterogeneous, exhibiting significant spatial patterns associated with a variety of SEDOH. These findings are consistent with a broad range of geospatial studies linking CVD outcomes to neighborhood-level characteristics. Across these studies, the association between CVD and SEDOH can be broadly categorized into three groups. The first group relates to socio-economic and demographic factors (Ford and Highfield 2016; Weimann et al. 2016). The second group encompasses climate and environmental exposures (Lim et al. 2014; Yan et al. 2023; Nawaro et al. 2024; Liang et al. 2025). The third group includes supportive healthcare resources, particularly access to healthcare services (Root et al. 2013).

Despite these substantial efforts to understand the epidemiological and spatial characteristics of CVD, much of the existing literature has relied on univariate spatial analyses using global and local spatial statistics to detect spatial clustering of CVD mortality or incidence (Faka et al. 2024; Jordan et al. 2024; Zangeneh et al. 2024). While these methods effectively identify spatial patterns, they provide limited inferential insight into the complex effects of multiple SEDOH.

To the best of our knowledge, few studies have conducted a comprehensive spatial inferential analysis of HVD that integrates a set of SEDOH derived from both open-source data and attributes extracted from clinical records. This research addresses this gap by examining the relationship between HVD and a comprehensive SEDOH dataset using a multi-step analytical approach. By doing so, this research provides richer inferential insights regarding the spatial patterns of HVD and their critical determinants.

3. Data and Methodology

This research adopts a multi-step analytical framework to investigate individual-level determinants of health outcomes and their spatial pattern at the LSOA scale. Figure 1 illustrates the flow of the methodological framework of this research.

Figure 1 Flowchart of the analytical framework

All individual-level analysis was performed in the Bart’s Secure Data Environment. In the first step, individual-level risk is modeled using logistic regression, where the binary response variable indicates whether an individual was diagnosed with HVD. For explanatory variables, the PREDICT (Preventing Decompensation using Informatics and Clinical Testing) cohort records collected by NHS Barts Health Trust are utilized. The study cohort comprises 10,000 adult patients (≥ 18 years) residing in Northeast London who underwent transthoracic echocardiography between 2015 and 2025. NLP techniques are used to extract the presence (positive cases) or absence (negative cases) of severe valvular disease diagnoses. Structured electronic health record data are linked with variables extracted from unstructured clinical narratives using NLP. The explanatory variables in the first-step logistic regression include socio-demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, and ethnicity, derived from NLP-based bag-of-words representations of clinical text. In addition to the cohort records, two environmental exposure variables—the PM10 level¹ (small particles with a diameter of 10 micrometers or less) as an air quality indicator, and the neighborhood greenspace proportion² as a measure of the green environment—are integrated into the individual-level data based on patients’ LSOA of residence.

In the intermediate step, the individual risk profiles obtained from the logistic regression are linked to LSOA-level population structures using iterative proportional fitting (IPF) and post-stratification, thereby reducing sampling bias and ensuring the risk estimates are spatially representative. IPF is a microsimulation method used to construct synthetic joint population distribution when only marginal distributions (e.g., by ethnicity and gender) are available from census data. Starting from an initial distribution informed by the sample of Barts patients, the IPF procedure iteratively adjusts cell values so that the joint distribution result matches known marginal totals for each dimension. The resulting synthetic population represents the estimated composition of individuals within each LSOA. This synthetic population is then combined with the fitted probabilities from the logistic regression to compute the mean HVD risk at the LSOA level, by aggregating individual-level predicted risks weighted by the synthesized population counts. The estimated mean risk is subsequently used as input for spatial analysis alongside open-source SEDOH data.

In the final step, spatial analysis focuses on LSOA-level Northeast London, comprising four boroughs: City of London, Tower Hamlets, Newham, and Waltham Forest. This area contains 506 LSOAs. The

¹ Gridded Emissions Data of PM10 from NAEI (National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory) Air Pollutant Emissions Data is utilized (<https://naei.energysecurity.gov.uk/data/maps/download-gridded-emissions>).

² Ordnance Survey (OS) Open Greenspace data is utilized to calculate the proportion of greenspace in LSOA (<https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/products/os-open-greenspace>).

spatial extent is defined based on the coverage of clinical records collected from five hospitals operating under NHS Barts Health Trust, as the majority of patient records originate from residents within these boroughs. Exploratory spatial data analysis is first conducted to detect spatial clustering of the mean risk using local spatial autocorrelation measures. Subsequently, eigenvector spatial filtering (ESF) regression is employed to examine the relationships between area-level mean risk and SEDOH. As proxies for SEDOH at the LSOA level, seven sub-indices from the 2025 Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) are used as explanatory variables in the ESF regression model.

This multi-step framework enables a clear separation between individual-level risk estimation and area-level spatial pattern analysis, facilitating interpretable inference across scales.

4. Preliminary Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the results of the individual-level logistic regression. The age variable is excluded from the model because most HVD patients are over 65 years old, making this variable redundant. The White group in the ethnicity variable, as well as the PM10 level of an individual’s neighborhood, show statistically significant odds ratios, indicating that ethnicity and air quality are significantly associated with the incidence of HVD. Although the male variable (relative to the baseline category – female) is not significant at the 95% level (p -value = 0.057), it still suggests a potential relationship between gender and HVD incidence.

The White group exhibits higher odds of HVD incidence (odds ratio = 1.277), indicating that White patients have approximately 1.28 times higher odds of having HVD compared to the baseline group (Asian). In addition, individuals living in neighborhoods with lower PM10 levels tend to have higher odds of HVD incidence. This finding is contrary to typical expectations, as better air quality is generally associated with improved health outcomes. One possible explanation is that this result reflects a form of residential preference/sorting where older individuals, who carry a higher baseline risk for HVD, may be more likely to live in neighbourhoods with cleaner air that are also more car-dependent and less walkable. As a result, environmental exposure variables may exhibit a negative association with HVD incidence, due to the underlying population composition of neighborhoods and other unobserved contextual factors.

Table 1 Individual level logistic regression results

Variable		Odds ratio	Confidence interval (95%)	z-value	p-value
Intercept		0.411	[0.127, 1.325]	-1.489	0.137
Gender (Baseline: Female)	Male	0.874	[0.760, 1.004]	-1.906	0.057
Ethnicity (Baseline: Asian)	Black	1.030	[0.818, 1.296]	0.249	0.803
	Others	1.289	[0.752, 1.407]	0.178	0.859
	White	1.277	[1.090, 1.496]	3.027	0.002**
Environmental exposure	PM10	0.911	[0.846, 0.980]	-2.511	0.012*
	Green space	0.998	[0.993, 1.003]	-0.641	0.522

Note: * 95% significant, ** 99% significant

The fitted values from the logistic regression represent the predicted probability of HVD risk given individual characteristics. For the second-step spatial analysis, these predicted probabilities are aggregated to calculate the mean HVD risk at the LSOA level, using 2021 Census population information in conjunction with an IPF procedure. The resulting mean risk is then used as the response variable in the spatial regression model.

Figure 2-a illustrates the spatial distribution of the mean HVD risk. Figure 2-b presents the spatial autocorrelation of the mean risk using local Moran’s I , indicating strong positive spatial autocorrelation in its distribution (global Moran’s $I = 0.90$, p -value < 0.001), which suggests substantial spatial clustering. The spatial pattern indicates that neighborhoods in the northern part of the study area (red in Figure 2-b) exhibit higher estimated risk compared to those in the southeastern part (blue in Figure

2-b). Specifically, high HVD risk areas are clustered in the northern part of the study area, including most parts of Waltham Forest in Outer London, while the City of London and Tower Hamlets form a large cluster of low HVD risk areas in Inner London.

Figure 2 Mean risk map and spatial autocorrelation

Table 2 shows the results of the ESF regression between the mean HVD risk and the IMD 2025³ deprivation sub-indices (scores). The results indicate that Income, Health, Barriers to Services, and Living Environment variables are statistically significant and are associated with the mean HVD risk at the LSOA level. All four variables are negatively associated with the response variable, implying that higher HVD risk is observed in less deprived areas across multiple dimensions of deprivation. This finding is consistent with the results from the individual-level analysis, where higher HVD probability is associated counterintuitively with better environmental conditions. One possible explanation is that this pattern may reflect residential preferences and sorting among older populations, who may be more likely to reside in less busy and deprived areas with cleaner air that might be less walkable.

Table 2 ESF regression results

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	Confidence interval (95%)	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value
Intercept	0.0968	0.001	[0.095, 0.099]	105.055	<0.001**
Income	-0.0084	0.003	[-0.013, 0.003]	-3.324	0.001**
Employment	0.0065	0.006	[-0.006, 0.019]	1.021	0.308
Education	-0.00001	0.000	[-0.000, 0.000]	-0.046	0.963
Health	-0.0014	0.000	[-0.001, -0.001]	-3.364	0.001**
Crime	0.0001	0.000	[-0.000, -0.000]	0.310	0.757
Barriers	-0.0001	0.000	[-0.000, -0.000]	-3.845	<0.001**
Living	-0.00008	0.000	[-0.000, -0.000]	-4.727	<0.001**

Note: * 95% significant, ** 99% significant

Figure 3 depicts the spatial distribution of the residuals (Figure 3-a) and fitted values (Figure 3-b) of the mean HVD risk based on the ESF regression results. The distribution of the residuals, along with the global Moran's *I* value (-0.251, *p*-value < 0.001), suggests that the ESF specification effectively

³ English indices of deprivation 2025 (<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2025>).

accounts for the positive spatial autocorrelation present in the data and removes residual spatial dependence from the model. The fitted values from the ESF regression also successfully identify areas with high HVD risk, showing strong consistency with the spatial pattern of mean HVD risk illustrated in Figure 2-a.

Figure 3 Spatial distribution of the residuals and fitted values of the mean risk

5. Concluding Remarks

This research examines the spatial patterns of HVD incidence and their relationships with a comprehensive set of SEDOH. The findings are expected to identify high-risk neighborhoods for HVD incidence, clarify the association between HVD and SEDOH at both the individual and spatial levels, and determine the critical factors – ethnicity, air quality, living environment – that strongly correlated with HVD risk. Extended analyses with a larger patient dataset and the inclusion of unobserved covariates like built environment metrics may be helpful to disentangle environmental effects from residential sorting.

Building on the identification of critical SEDOH associated with HVD incidence, future research will extend these findings to applied spatial decision-making. In particular, location modeling of cardiac testing sites will be developed to improve the efficiency of early HVD detection. By explicitly incorporating neighborhood-level SEDOH characteristics into location models, this line of research aims to support more equitable access to cardiovascular diagnosis and care.

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References

- Biswas, D., Wu, J., Brown, S., Bharucha, A., Fairhurst, N., Kaye, G., ... & O’Gallagher, K. (2025). Racial and ethnic disparities in aortic stenosis within a universal healthcare system characterized by natural language processing for targeted intervention. *European Heart Journal-Digital Health*, 6(3), 392-403.
- Coffey, S., Cairns, B. J., & Iung, B. (2015). The modern epidemiology of heart valve disease. *Heart*, 102(1), 75-85.
- Coffey, S., Roberts-Thomson, R., Brown, A., Carapetis, J., Chen, M., Enriquez-Sarano, M., ... & Prendergast, B. D. (2021). Global epidemiology of valvular heart disease. *Nature Reviews*

Cardiology, 18(12), 853-864.

d'Arcy, J. L., Coffey, S., Loudon, M. A., Kennedy, A., Pearson-Stuttard, J., Birks, J., ... & Prendergast, B. D. (2016). Large-scale community echocardiographic screening reveals a major burden of undiagnosed valvular heart disease in older people: the OxVALVE Population Cohort Study. *European heart journal*, 37(47), 3515-3522.

Faka, A., Chalkias, C., Damigou, E., Chrysohoou, C., Barkas, F., Dalmyras, D., ... & Panagiotakos, D. (2024). Exploring Spatiotemporal Patterns of Cardiovascular Disease in Greece: Insights from the ATTICA Study (2002-2022). *European Journal of Geography*, 15(4), 271-280.

Ford, M. M., & Highfield, L. D. (2016). Exploring the spatial association between social deprivation and cardiovascular disease mortality at the neighborhood level. *PloS one*, 11(1), e0146085.

Jordan, G., Ridder, D., Joost, S., Vollenweider, P., Preisig, M., Marques-Vidal, P., ... & Vaucher, J. (2024). Spatial analysis of 10-year predicted risk and incident atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease: the CoLaus cohort. *Scientific reports*, 14(1), 4752.

Liang, J., Deng, S., Yang, H., Zhu, S., & Zheng, R. (2025). Spatiotemporal effects of urban micro-scale built environment on cardiovascular diseases. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 17193.

Lim, Y. R., Bae, H. J., Lim, Y. H., Yu, S., Kim, G. B., & Cho, Y. S. (2014). Spatial analysis of PM10 and cardiovascular mortality in the Seoul metropolitan area. *Environmental health and toxicology*, 29, e2014005.

Mena, C., Sepúlveda, C., Fuentes, E., Ormazábal, Y., & Palomo, I. (2018). Spatial analysis for the epidemiological study of cardiovascular diseases: A systematic literature search. *Geospatial health*, 13(1).

Nawaro, J., Gianquinteri, L., Pagliosa, A., Sechi, G. M., & Caiani, E. G. (2024). Neighborhood determinants of vulnerability to heat for cardiovascular health: a spatial analysis of Milan, Italy. *Population and Environment*, 46(4), 25.

Root, E. D., Gonzales, L., Persse, D. E., Hinchey, P. R., McNally, B., & Sasson, C. (2013). A tale of two cities: the role of neighborhood socioeconomic status in spatial clustering of bystander CPR in Austin and Houston. *Resuscitation*, 84(6), 752-759.

Weimann, A., Dai, D., & Oni, T. (2016). A cross-sectional and spatial analysis of the prevalence of multimorbidity and its association with socioeconomic disadvantage in South Africa: A comparison between 2008 and 2012. *Social Science & Medicine* (1982), 163, 144.

Yan, S., Liu, G., & Chen, X. (2023). Spatiotemporal distribution characteristics and influencing factors of the rate of cardiovascular hospitalization in Ganzhou city of China. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*, 10, 1225878.

Yeung, M., Kerrigan, J., Sodhi, S., Huang, P. H., Novak, E., Maniar, H., & Zajarias, A. (2013). Racial differences in rates of aortic valve replacement in patients with severe aortic stenosis. *The American journal of cardiology*, 112(7), 991-995.

Zangeneh, A., Najafi, F., Khosravi, A., Ziapour, A., Molavi, H., Moradi, Z., ... & Soofi, M. (2024). Epidemiological patterns and spatiotemporal analysis of cardiovascular disease mortality in Iran: Development of public health strategies and policies. *Current Problems in Cardiology*, 49(8), 102675.

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